

Comprehensive multiparameter genetic analysis improves circulating tumor DNA detection in head and neck cancer patients

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Tumor-specific genetic aberrations in cell-free DNA (cfDNA) from plasma are promising biomarkers for diagnosis of recurrent head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC). However, the sensitivity when using somatic mutations only in cfDNA is suboptimal. Here, we combined detection of copy number aberrations (CNAs), human papillomavirus (HPV) DNA and somatic mutations in a single sequencing workflow. **Methods:** Pretreatment plasmas of 40 patients and 20 non-cancer controls were used for analysis. Plasma DNA underwent low-coverage whole genome sequencing (lcWGS) to detect both CNAs and HPV-DNA, and deep sequencing to detect mutations in 12 frequently altered cancer driver genes in HNSCC using the same sequencing library. A specific analysis pipeline line was developed for data mining. The corresponding tumors were analyzed using slightly adapted protocols.

Results: Using the developed method, somatic mutations and CNAs were detected in plasma DNA of HNSCC patients in 67% and 52%, respectively. HPV-DNA in plasma was detected in 100% of patients with HPV-positive tumors, and not in plasma of patients with HPV-negative tumors or non-cancer controls. Combined analysis increased the detection rate of tumor DNA in plasma to 78%. The detection rate was significantly associated with the stage of disease of the tumor. Neither HPV status nor location of the primary tumor influenced detection of CNAs or somatic mutations in plasma.

Conclusions: This study demonstrates that the combined analysis of CNAs, HPV and somatic mutations in plasma of HNSCC patients is feasible and contributes to a higher sensitivity of the assay compared to single modality analyses.

Introduction

Head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC) shows a high rate of recurrences, distant metastasis and second primary tumors [1], which can often only be treated curatively when detected at an early stage. Consequently, there is an imperative need for the development of minimally invasive methods that allow early detection of relapsed disease, but such a biomarker is currently not available. Therefore, diagnosis of recurrent HNSCC remains dependent on conventional imaging and clinical examination, resulting in many patients being diagnosed with recurrent disease at an advanced stage. The introduction of next-generation sequencing (NGS) created new opportunities for post-treatment surveillance. A promising example of NGS applications

is the detection of circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) in plasma, that was first described in colorectal cancer [2] and later also in HNSCC [3].

In a previous study, Wang et al. studied the detection of somatic mutations and HPV in cell-free DNA (cfDNA) from plasma and saliva of 93 patients [4]. The authors focused on somatic mutations and HPV using a PCR-amplification based sequencing protocol. Limitations of this approach are: (i) it requires selection of mutations from the index tumor, followed by custom primer design for each unique mutation while even cancer driver mutations in the recurrent tumor may differ from those in the index tumor [5]; and (ii) the protocol is complex including a gel-purification step, which may introduce cross-contamination [6]. A more general limitation of PCR-based approaches lies in the fact that ctDNA fragments are generally small, on average

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Table 1
Patient characteristics.

Characteristic	N = 40
Age, mean (SD)	65.6 (9)
Gender	
Male (%)	27 (67.5)
Female (%)	13 (32.5)
Smoking (PY)	
0–10 (%)	11 (27.5)
11–24 (%)	8 (20)
> 24 (%)	21 (52.5)
Subsite	
Oral cavity (%)	5 (12.5)
Oropharynx (%)	18 (45)
Hypopharynx (%)	10 (25)
Larynx (%)	5 (12.5)
Unknown primary (%)	2 (5)
TNM stage	
I (%)	2 (5)
II (%)	4 (10)
III (%)	6 (15)
IV (%)	28 (70)
T-stage	
0 (%)	2 (5)
1 (%)	3 (7.5)
2 (%)	13 (32.5)
3 (%)	4 (10)
4 (%)	18 (45)
N-stage	
0 (%)	17 (42.5)
1 (%)	7 (17.5)
2 (%)	15 (37.5)
3 (%)	1 (2.5)
HPV ^a	
Negative (%)	9 (45)
Positive (%)	10 (50)
Unknown ^b (%)	1 (5)

Abbreviation: HPV, human papilloma virus; PY, packyears; SD, standard deviation.

^a Only determined when primary tumor was located in oropharynx or unknown.

^b No material available from primary tumor for HPV analysis.

Fig. 1. Illustration of workflow for detection of ctDNA. Four ml of pretreatment plasma was used for automated DNA isolation and adapter ligation. The resulting library was divided in two to have a diagnostic backup, amplified, and subsequently used for low-coverage whole-genome sequencing to detect copy number aberrations and HPV, and target enrichment for deep sequencing to detect somatic mutations. Abbreviations: CNA, copy number aberrations; HPV, human papillomavirus; PCR, polymerase chain reaction; PE, paired-end; SE, single-end; WGS, whole genome sequencing.

Methods

Samples

We studied samples from 40 HNSCC patients and 20 anonymous individuals without cancer. The study was approved by the institutional review board and from all subjects signed informed consent was obtained. Patients were treated at Amsterdam UMC, location VUmc. Anonymous blood donors at Sanquin in Amsterdam served as non-cancer controls. Patient characteristics are depicted in Table 1. The control plasma was obtained from anonymized blood donors, and no clinical data was available. Samples of 4 × 6 ml whole blood were taken from patients before treatment of the primary tumor (N = 38) or before salvage treatment (N = 2) using EDTA vacutainers. Plasma was collected within 24 h from whole blood by centrifugation, and further purified with an additional centrifugation step at 20,162 g using a Hettich EBA 12 R microcentrifuge (Hettich, Tuttlingen, Germany) to

Table 2
Summary of detected tumor associated aberrations in cell-free DNA of plasma.

	Patient	Tumor location	Stage of disease	HPV	Number of CNAs in tumor	CNAs found in Plasma	Number of somatic mutations in Tumor	Number of somatic mutations in Plasma	HPV found in Plasma	Combined detection conclusion	
Tumor status known	590	hp	IVA		43	Yes	2	2	No	Yes	
	595	hp	IVC		31	Yes	4	4	No	Yes	
	598	hp	IVB		51	Yes	2	2	No	Yes	
	603	op	IVA	HPV16	18	Yes	4	0	HPV16	Yes	
	604	la	III		5	No	7	0	No	No	
	606	hp	III		36	No	4	2	No	Yes	
	607	la	III		40	No	2	1	No	Yes	
	610	oc	II		12	No	6	0	No	No	
	616	op	IVC	HPV16	23	Yes	5	2	HPV16	Yes	
	617	op	IVA	HPV16	3	Yes	0	NA ^a	HPV16	Yes	
	618	la	IVA		53	Yes	1	1	No	Yes	
	619	op	III	Negative	72	No	1	1	No	Yes	
	623	hp	IVA		50	Yes	1	1	No	Yes	
	625	op	IVA	HPV16	14	No	1	1	HPV16	Yes	
	626	oc	IVA		23	Yes	4	3	No	Yes	
	627	op	IVA	HPV16	16	No	2	1 ^b	NA ^c	Yes	
	628	op	IVB	Negative	30	No	6	1	No	Yes	
	629	hp	IVA		58	No	4	0	No	No	
	632	la	III		39	No	2	0	No	No	
	633	op	IVA	Negative	48	Yes	6	4	No	Yes	
	635	op	IVA	Negative	62	Yes	2	2	No	Yes	
	636	oc	I		0	NA ^d	6	0	No	No	
	639	op	IVA	Negative	43	Yes	2	2	No	Yes	
	640	op	IVA	HPV16	13	No	2	0	HPV16	Yes	
	642	hp	II		61	No	1	0	No	No	
	647	la	IVA		23	Yes	2	2	No	Yes	
	649	hp	IVA		43	Yes	3	2	No	Yes	
	Tumor status unknown	591	op	II	HPV16	NA	No	NA	0	HPV16	Yes
		592	op	IVA	Unknown ^e	NA	No	NA	1	No	Yes
		601	oc	I		NA	No	NA	0	No	No
		608	oc	IVA		NA	Yes	NA	1	No	Yes
		611	up	IVB	Negative	NA	Yes	NA	1	No	Yes
		612	up	IVA	Negative	NA	Yes	NA	0	No	Yes
615		hp	IVA		NA	No	NA	2	No	Yes	
622		op	IVA	Negative	NA	No	NA	0	No	No	
630		op	III	HPV16	NA	No	NA	0	HPV16	Yes	
637		op	II	Negative	NA	No	NA	0	No	No	
643		op	IVA	HPV16	NA	Yes	NA	0	HPV16	Yes	
644		hp	IVA		NA	Yes	NA	0	No	Yes	
648		Op	IVA	HPV16	NA	No	NA	0	HPV16	Yes	

Abbreviation: CNA, copy number aberration; hp, hypopharynx; HPV, human papillomavirus; la, larynx; NA, not applicable; oc, oral cavity; op, oropharynx; up, unknown primary.

^a No somatic mutations present in primary tumor.

^b Found only in backup half of pre-PCR ligation product.

^c Corrupted backup FASTQ file.

^d No CNAs present in primary tumor.

^e No material available from primary tumor for HPV analysis.

remove contaminating cells. The schematic workflow of plasma DNA isolation, library preparation and sequencing is depicted in Fig. 1. The cfDNA from 4 ml plasma was isolated using a Qiasymphony automated platform (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). Extra tumor biopsies could be obtained from 27 patients during examination under general anesthesia and were directly snap-frozen and stored in liquid nitrogen. Tumor DNA was isolated using the Purelink™ Genomic DNA Mini Kit (cat. K182001, Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) after macrodissection to ensure that neoplastic cellularity was over 20%. The actual tumor-derived fraction was later precisely quantified from lcWGS using the R package ACE [12].

NGS library preparation and lcWGS

Plasma NGS libraries were generated with a 5500 SOLiD™ Fragment Library kit (cat. 4464412, LifeTech, Carlsbad, CA, USA) and TruSeq adapters (cat. FC-121-4001 and FC-121-4002, Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) using a Biomek FX robot (Beckman Coulter, Pasadena, CA, USA). Prior to downstream steps, the plasma sequencing library was divided

in a diagnostic library (20 µl) and a backup library (25 µl), and the diagnostic library underwent 12 cycles of PCR duplication (Fig. 1) to generate the fragments for sequencing and allow equimolar pooling. Tumor NGS libraries were manually generated using the KAPA Hyper Prep Kit (cat. 07962347001, KAPA Biosystems, Cape Town, South Africa). Next, lcWGS was performed on the plasma and tumor samples by sequencing the non-enriched NGS libraries using an Illumina HiSeq 2000 instrument (Illumina) with 50 bp single-end reads as described before [13,14] with 8 to 21 samples per lane.

Target enrichment and deep sequencing

Amplified diagnostic NGS libraries were enriched using a SeqCap EZ Choice kit (cat. 06740251001, Roche Nimblegen, Madison, WI, USA) with a 66 kb custom library of the exons of 12 genes (*AJUBA*, *CASP8*, *CDKN2A*, *FAT1*, *FBXW7*, *HRAS*, *KMT2D*, *NOTCH1*, *NSD1*, *PIK3CA*, *PTEN*, *TP53*) that were selected based on TCGA data as the most frequently altered cancer driver genes in HNSCC [11]. The enriched libraries were subsequently sequenced on an Illumina HiSeq or Illumina

Fig. 2. Example of tumor and corresponding plasma copy number profile. Absolute copy number profile of a cT4aN3M1 hypopharynx tumor (A) and corresponding plasma sample (B) showing, amongst others, well known losses of 3p, 9p and 17p, gains of 1q and 3q, and high-level amplifications of 7p and 11q. 2n ploidy was assumed for both samples. The graphs depict the number of copies on the Y-axis and the bins ordered by chromosomal location on the X-axis. Plot was derived from ACE.

HiSeq instrument with 125 bp or 150 bp paired-end reads.

Bioinformatics and statistical analysis

Specific pipelines to detect CNAs, HPV and somatic mutations in both tumor and plasma DNA are described in the Supplemental Methods and Fig. S1. Clinical characteristics of patients with ctDNA detected in plasma were compared to those of patients without ctDNA detected in plasma using Fisher's exact test. All statistical analyses were performed using package 'stats' version 3.1.2 in R.

Results

Detection of copy number aberrations in tumor and corresponding plasma

First, 27 tumors, of which biopsies were available, were analyzed for presence of CNAs. On average, each tumor had 34 altered segments (range 0–72, Table 2), including well known losses of 3p, 9p, and 17p, and gains of 3q, 7p and 8q (Fig. S2). Next, the corresponding cfDNA was sequenced. The CNA profiles of tumor and plasma were compared for corresponding aberrations. An example is shown in Fig. 2. Alterations were found in 14 out of 27 (52%) plasma samples (Fig. 3A and Table 2), whereas in 20 controls, a deletion was detected in only one

case (5%) ($P < 0.01$ by Fisher's Exact test). This deletion was found in an area with known copy number variations (4q31.21, database of genomic variants (<http://dgv.tcag.ca>)), and most likely depicts a copy number variation (CNV) and not a somatic genetic change.

Detection of somatic mutations in tumor and corresponding plasma

For detection of somatic mutations, the same sequencing library used for copy number analysis was enriched for the 12-gene targeted sequencing panel. The mean coverage for plasma was 478 (range 145–1464). The distribution of the coverage of each gene in the plasma DNA is depicted in Fig. S3 for the samples with the highest coverage (A, mean 1464) and lowest coverage (B, mean 145). On average, the tumors contained three somatic mutations in the selected genes (range 0–7) with a mean variant allele frequency (VAF) of 29.3 (range 1.1–87.3) (Table S1). Next, these mutations were searched for in the sequencing data of the plasma DNA using the bioinformatics pipelines depicted in Fig. S1C. One or more somatic mutations of the index tumor were detected in the plasma of 18 of 27 (67%) patients (Table 2 and Table S1).

HPV detection

An algorithm was developed to map reads from lcWGS to HPV genomes. This algorithm was first evaluated by comparing the results from tumor DNA lcWGS to the results of a validated HPV test to confirm that it could indeed be used for HPV detection [15]. We found 100% agreement in the HPV-positive and HPV-negative tumors analyzed. Next, the developed algorithm was applied to plasma DNA lcWGS, and HPV was detected in plasma of all evaluable patients with HPV-positive tumors (Table 2, Fig. S4). One sample (592) was not evaluable for this analysis as the backup FASTQ file was corrupted that was required for HPV genome mapping. No false-positive results were detected in plasma of patients with HPV-negative tumors or non-cancer controls (Table 2, Fig. S4) at the chosen cut-off value.

Detection of ctDNA without prior knowledge of tumor DNA aberrations

Since the algorithms to detect CNAs in plasma are not dependent on knowledge of tumor DNA aberrations, the same methods were applied to the 13 cases of which genetic data of the tumor was not available. CNAs were detected in plasma of 5 of 13 patients (38%, Table 2 and Fig. 3). For detection of somatic mutations in plasma without prior knowledge of the somatic mutations in the primary tumor we took additional precautions. More stringent criteria for mutation calling were applied to ensure a low number of false positive mutation calls. Using these criteria, mutations were called in plasma of 4 of 13 patients (31%, Table 2). It should be noted that when we applied these criteria to the 27 patients with known tumor mutation status (Table S2), some mutations were identified in cfDNA that were not identified in the primary tumor. These calls may be false positive, but could also relate to another (patho)biological process.

Combined analysis of CNA, HPV-DNA and somatic mutations

The combined analysis of CNAs, somatic mutations and HPV in patients with known tumor DNA aberrations revealed tumor-associated aberrations in plasma DNA of 21 out of 27 (78%) patients (Table 2). When prior knowledge of tumor DNA aberrations was not available, ctDNA was detected in plasma of 10 of 13 patients (77%). Combining the results of cfDNA analyses in patients with and without prior knowledge on tumor variants, resulted in ctDNA detection in 31 out of 40 patients (78%, Table 2).

Fig. 3. Heatmap of copy number aberrations in tumor and plasma samples. (A) For each of 27 patients, copy number aberrations found in plasma, first row, and in tumor, second row, are shown. On the X-axis are the segments ordered by chromosomal location. Blue indicates an allelic loss (less than two copies), whereas red indicates an allelic gain or amplification (more than two copies). On the right, the correlation is shown between segments of plasma and tumor. (B) For the 13 patients with missing tumor data, only the plasma copy number aberrations are shown.

Influence of clinical factors

In this cohort, the detection of CNAs and somatic mutations in plasma was not influenced by the location of the primary tumor or the HPV status (oropharynx tumors only). However, the TNM-stage was positively correlated to detection of CNAs in plasma ($P < 0.05$), and to mutations in plasma ($P < 0.05$) (Fig. S5).

Analyses to improve sensitivity

To determine whether sequencing coverage constituted a rate-limiting factor in our experiments, we resequenced the index library of plasma of three patients using similar sequencing parameters and combined the sequencing results of the first and second run. Despite the increase in the total number of reads, the combined mean coverage was very comparable to the mean coverage of the two separate runs after duplicate removal, and no additional variants were discovered (Table S3), indicating that the libraries were sequenced to completion with sufficient coverage.

Next, we prepared target-enriched sequencing libraries from the backup plasma DNA library (Fig. 1) of seven patients, which may contain additional DNA templates that were not sequenced before. In one patient without mutations in the primary plasma DNA library, ctDNA was detected in the backup library (Table S3). These results demonstrate that input DNA can be the limiting factor for detection of tumor variants in plasma.

Discussion

This study was designed to develop a workflow for detection of CNAs, HPV-DNA and somatic mutations in cfDNA from plasma of HNSCC patients using the same sequencing library, and to determine its performance in plasma samples of 40 HNSCC patients. This method was based on lcWGS for detection of CNAs and HPV-DNA, and targeted deep sequencing of a panel of 12 frequently mutated genes in HNSCC.

In our view this approach combines the best of all available approaches, and we detected CNAs in plasma of HNSCC patients in 52%, HPV-DNA in plasma of 100% of patients with HPV-positive tumors, and somatic mutations in plasma of 67% of HNSCC patients. It was hypothesized that the combined analysis of CNA, HPV and mutations would increase the overall sensitivity of the assay, and this was indeed the case. To reduce costs, one could argue for a stepwise approach, in which first lcWGS is performed to detect CNAs and HPV-DNA, and deep sequencing only when CNAs or HPV-DNA are not detected. In fact, for HPV-positive tumors, our data suggests that the deep sequencing step is redundant since all HPV-positive tumors could already be detected by lcWGS. Other authors demonstrated different HPV-DNA detection methods [16–20], but the major advantage of our combined approach is that it is comprehensive: a single assay that serves all tumor subtypes.

As genetic alterations in the index and recurrent tumor may differ [5], ideally post-treatment surveillance does not rely only on detection of genetic changes that were present in the index tumor. In this regard, we show an additional advantage of our comprehensive method. Confident detection of somatic mutations without prior knowledge of tumor DNA mutations may be hampered by false positive calls, but the detection of CNAs and HPV-DNA in plasma did not depend on prior knowledge and can therefore be applied directly to plasma DNA with high specificity (> 95%).

To our best knowledge relatively few studies focus on the detection of ctDNA in HNSCC patients. Wang et al. detected ctDNA in 87% of 47 HNSCC patients [4]. Importantly, their assay also included detection of circulating HPV-DNA in patients with HPV-positive tumors, whereby the sensitivity increased from 64% to 87%. Schwaederle et al. found alterations in plasma of 88% of 25 HNSCC patients [21]. However, these alterations were not matched to the mutational profiles of the primary tumors, which in our study was shown to be important to

exclude false positive calls. Perdomo et al. detected mutations in 42% of 36 HNSCC cases [22], Schirmer et al. showed a sensitivity of 74% [9], and Galot et al. showed a sensitivity of 51% [23]. In other studies [3,7] only very small HNSCC patient cohorts were analyzed, which makes a relevant comparison difficult.

There are several options to further enhance the detection rate, which might be required for clinical implementation. First, it was shown by others that methods of blood processing have a strong influence on cfDNA levels [24], and optimizing the sampling of blood by using dedicated cell-free DNA tubes may improve detection. Second, increasing the DNA input may overcome undersampling and improve detection of low fractions of ctDNA [25]. This effect was already shown in our study as we detected additional variants when sequencing the backup DNA library, and it further implies that a high conversion rate, i.e. the representation of the cfDNA in the sequencing library, is of large importance. Third, ctDNA has shorter fragment sizes than non-tumor derived plasma DNA [26], and size selection of fragments between 90 and 150 bp was shown to improve the detection of ctDNA in advanced cancers [27]. Finally, Wang et al. showed that the combination of saliva and plasma analysis also increased sensitivity [4], which implies that future cohort studies should also include samples of saliva or oral rinses from HNSCC patients.

In conclusion, we developed a method for combined analysis of somatic mutations, HPV-DNA and CNAs in cfDNA from plasma of HNSCC patients. Although prior knowledge of the genetic changes in the tumor is helpful in the analyses, we show that it is not required. Future research should focus on implementing the suggested improvements of the assay and application in a large longitudinal cohort for early detection of recurrent disease to proof the clinical utility.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oraloncology.2020.104852>.

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